

EFFECTS OF SAND BOX (*Hura crepitans*) SEED MEALS ON RATS' LIVER AND SERUM ENZYME LEVELS

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ABSTRACT

The effect of *Hura crepitans* seed flour, incorporated at 10% (w/w) protein on liver and serum acid phosphatase (E.C. 3.1.3.2), alkaline phosphatase (E.C.3.1.3.1), aspartate – amino transferase activity (AST) (E.C.2.6.1.1) and alanine amino transferase activity (ALT) (E.C.2.6.1.2) activities were investigated. Generally, results of the toxicological investigation showed that acid phosphatase (ACP), alkaline phosphatase (ALP), aspartate amino transferase (AST) and alanine amino transferase (ALT) activities of liver and serum of rats fed on defatted cooked diet were not significantly different ($p>0.05$) from those of control fed casein diet. However, their activities were significantly reduced ($p\leq 0.05$) in liver of rats fed with undefatted cooked diet, raw defatted diet and raw undefatted diet, while those of serum were significantly increased ($p\leq 0.05$). The results of this study indicated that combination of defatting and cooking processes reduced the toxicity of *Hura crepitans* seeds.

KEYWORDS; Sandbox, *Hura crepitans*, toxicity, liver and serum.

INTRODUCTION

Hura crepitans Linn is a tropical plant belonging to the family Euphorbiaceae. In Nigeria, it is known as 'Odan Mecca' by the Kabba people of Kogi State and "Aroyin" by the Ijesha People of Osun State. *Hura crepitans* is often planted in towns and villages as a cover tree. It has short, densely crowned spines on the trunk and branches, the long-stalked leaves with prominent closely parallel pinnate nerves, the purple flower spikes and the large fluted flattened, fruits are highly distinctive. This tree flowers usually at the beginning of and again at the end of rainy season. One nut is a flattened and fluted disc with 5 – 10 lobes about 2.5cm deep and 7.5cm wide on a stout stalk. The capsule splits explosively releasing one flattened circular seed about 18mm across from each chamber (Tropilab Inc. and Hear Organization).

It has been reported that a person who ate a seed of *Hura crepitans* complained of burning in the throat; vomiting and purging; suffocating and headache [Allen (2000); Clarke (2000)]. They further stressed that people who had eaten the shells with the seeds were seized with violent vomiting and headache while those who ate the seeds without the shell, suffered from nausea and violent pain in stomach, vomited once and violent diarrhea. A milky juice that is present in all parts of the *Hura* plant, can cause blindness, if applied (Allen ,2000). He also reported that oil of *Hura crepitans* is used as purgative. Despite all these negative findings against *hura crepitans* seed, the works of Fagbemi and Adebawale (2000), Adedire and Ajayi (2003) and Fowomola and Akindahunsi (2005) revealed that *Hura crepitans* seed is a nutritionally promising seed and more so, there is paucity of information on its toxicity on blood and liver of rats. The present study is aimed at providing this information.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Collection of Samples

Hura crepitans seed pods were collected from Ogidiri African Primary School, Offa, Kwara State, Nigeria. They were authenticated in the Department of Biology, School of Science, Federal University of Technology Akure, Ondo State, Nigeria. The samples were air dried in the laboratory for two weeks, Cotyledons were removed from the pods and ground to a mesh size of 1mm.

Methods

Chemical Analysis

Crude protein and lipid contents of each diet were determined using the methods described by (Horwitz,1980), ash content was determined by incineration at 500°C to a constant weight as described by (Pearson,1973) and crude

fibre was measured by using methods described by (Foster and Leslie,1971). Carbohydrate content of each diet was determined by using Clegg – Anthrone Method (Norman and Waddington,1989) .

Bioassay

Experimental Animal and Diets

A total of twenty – four male albino rats of Wistar strain were used. They were made up of four rats in each group and housed in individual steel cages. Animal grouping was performed on the bases of their body weights which were homogenously distributed within all groups. Six groups of rats were maintained on different protein diets as follows: Group I – control diet (Casein), Group II – basal diet (no protein), Group III – deffated cooked hura seed diet, Group IV – undafatted cooked hura seed diet, Group V – raw defatted hura seed diet and Group VI – raw underfatted hura seed diet. Quantities of protein sources incorporated were such as would keep the protein of each diet at a maximum of 10 percent as described by(A.O.A.C. ,1980). Water and feed were supplied adlibitum throughout the experimental period. Each of the experiment was run for seventeen days, three days for preliminary feeding (i.e acclimatization) and fourteen days for actual feeding.

Preparation of Samples for ALP, ACP, AST, and ALT Activities

At the end of the experiment, all rats were anaesthetized using chloroform. Blood samples were collected from dying rats by cardiac puncture using needle and syringe. Each blood sample collected was centrifuged for 15 min at 2,000 g in a centrifuge , serum was collected in a sterile bottle and kept inside a refrigerator at -4°C. The stomach and thoracic regions of each rat were cut opened, liver was removed , kept inside sterile bottles and refrigerated at -4°C for further studies. Each liver (1gm) was weighed and homogenized by using pestle and mortal already placed in ice. 1ml of triton detergent was added to achieve total disruption of the cell membrane. 4ml of (0.25M sucrose solution containing 10mM Tris buffer, pH 7.4) was added to the homogenate and used for analysis.

Determination of Enzyme Activities

Alkaline phosphatase (ALP) and acid phosphatase (ACP) activities were determined using the colorimetric methods described by(Wright *et.al.*,1972a; Wright *et.al.*,1972b).Aspartate – amino transferase (AST) and Alanine – amino transferase (ALT) activities were determined using the methods described by Reitman and Frankel (1957).

Statistical Analysis

All data were analyzed by one – way ANOVA ($P<0.05$) and least significant differences between treatment means were determined by Duncan’s multiple-range test ($P<0.05$) (Steel and Torrie,1980).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Figures 1-2 depict the effects of *Hura crepitans* seed meals on the ACP, ALP, AST and ALT activities of liver and serum of rats. In general, the activities of ACP, ALP, AST and ALT in liver of rats fed with deffated raw (diet V) and undefatted raw diets (diet VI) were significantly reduced ($P\leq 0.05$) compared with those of control (casein diet) (diet I). Conversely, defatted and undefatted raw diets caused a statistically significant increase in the serum of ACP, ALP, AST and ALT. However, there was no significant ($P\geq 0.05$) difference between those of control (casein diet) and defatted cooked diet (diet III).

Only increase in serum ALP measurements are clinically important as it suggests hepatobilliary diseases or increased osteoblastic activity (Baron *et.al.*, 1994). In addition, reduction in tissue levels of ACP and ALP activities with increase in their activities in serum could be associated with cell damage (Yakubu and Akanji ,2003; Buratai *et.al.*, 2003). High level of ACP in the blood may indicate prostate cancer, Guacher’s diseases (which is a lipid metabolism disorder), hyper parathroidsism or Paget’s disease (Nordenson, 2002).

Increase in AST and ALT activities in the blood plasma has been attributed to cell damages (Ottah *et.al.*,2003). ALT is thought to be a more specific indicator of liver inflammation, since AST may be elevated in diseases of other organs such as heart or muscle disease (David, and Johnson,1999).

The reduction of enzyme activities in liver was more pronounced in diets containing deffated raw (diet V) and undefatted raw (diet VI) *hura crepitans* seeds than those of defatted cooked (diet III) and undefatted cooked (diet

IV). This could be as a result of presence of antinutrients present in the former diets. The toxic effect of *Hura crepitans* seed attributed to the presence of tannins and hemagglutins in it (Adedire and Ajayi, 2003). Possible carcinogenesis is also evident by the production of liver cancer when tannins are applied to burns or administered subcutaneously repeatedly as reported by Bichel and Bach (1968). Furthermore, *Hura crepitans* being a member of *Euphorbiaceae* family has been reported to contain cyanide (Anosike and Ekwuatu, 1980). Cyanide is known for its inhibitory effect on Cytochrome oxidase in cell respiration (Oke, 1997).

CONCLUSION

The present research work has shown that defatting and cooking processes improved the nutritional quality of *Hura crepitans* seed. Therefore, they can be used to detoxify *Hura crepitans* seed before its incorporation into feeds.

REFERENCES

- Adedire and Ajayi (2003); Potential of Sand Box *Hura crepitans* Seed oil for Protection of Cowpea Seeds from Bruchidae Infestation. *Journal of Plant Diseases and Protection*. 110(6). 1-9.
- Allen, T. F (2000); *Hura crepitans*.L- the Encyclopedia of Pure Material Medical Pp. 1-2.
- Anosike, E. O. and Ekwuatu, C. K. (1980); Changes During the Fermentation of Castor Oil (*Rinus Communis*) Seeds for use as a Seasoning Agent. *Qualities Plant. P1. Foods. Human. Nutria.:* 30, 181 – 185.
- A.O.A.C. (1980) – Official Methods of Analysis of Analytical Chemists. 12th Edition. Washington, D.C.Pp.1-60.
- Baron, D. N., Wicher, J. T and Lee, K. E (1994). A New Short Textbook of Chemical Pathology. ELBS 5th Edition. Pp. 151 – 156.
- Bichel, J. and Bach, A. (1968); Investigation on the Toxicity of Small Chronic Doses of Tannic Acid with Special Reference to Possible Carcinogenicity. *Acta Pharmacol Toxicol* 36;Pp.41-45.
- Buratai L. B., Umar, I. A, Bello, H. and Gadaka, M. A. (2003); Biochemical and Haematological Changes Following Administration of Sub – Tethal does of Dimethoate in rats. *Book of Abstracts of 23rd Annual Conference of the Nigerian Society of Biochemistry and Molecular Biology, Ilorin, Nigerian.*Pp. 35-36.
- Clarke, J. H (2000); *Hura crepitans* . A Dictionary of Practical Material Medical. P 1-2.
- David, E. and Johnson, M. D (1999); Special Consideration in Interpreting Liver Function Tests; *American Family Physician*, Published by the American Academy of Family Physicians, <http://www.afp.Org/afp/990415/2223.htm/>
- Fagbemi, T. N and Adebowale, Y. A (2000) Food Potential of *Hura crepitans*. *Proceeding of the 24th Annual Conference of Nigeria Institute of Food Science & Technology (NIFST)Bauchi, Nigeria.*
- Fowomola M. A and Akindahunsi A. A (2005) Protein Quality Indices of Sandbox (*Hura crepitans*) seeds. *J. of Food, Agric and Environment* Vol. 3(2).
- Foster, D. S and Leslie, S. E (1971); In Crude Fibre. *Encyclopedia of Industrial Chemical Analysis*. Vol. II.Pp. 49 – 51.
- Horwitz, W. (1980); *Official Methods of Analysis* (13th Edition.Association of Official Analytical Chemical, Washington D.C U.S.A).
- Nordenson, N. J (2002) Acid Phosphatase Text. [http://www. Health atozconal heathatoz/atoz/ency/acid-phosphatase-test.html](http://www.Health.atozconal.heathatoz/atoz/ency/acid-phosphatase-test.html).
- Norman, R.O.C and Waddington, D. J (1989) .In *Carbohydrates. Modern Organic Chemistry* 4th Edition un win hyman Ltd. Pp.289-297.

Oke, D. B (1997) . Mechanism of Action, Toxicity and Nutritional Significance of Heat – Stable Anti-nutritional Factors in some Legumes. *A Review Nig. J. Nutria. Sci.* Vol. 18(2) 1-5.

Ottah, G. M., Wegwu M. O and Sule O. J (2003); The Effects of Water Soluble Fraction (WSF) of Crude Oil on some Biochemical Indices of *Clarias gariepinus* Book of Abstracts of 23rd Annual Conference of the Nigerian Society of Biochemistry and Molecular Biology. Ilorin, Nigeria.Pp. 37.

Pearson D. (1973) Laboratory Techniques in Food Analysis Butter Worth London.

Reitman, S.and Frankel, S. A. (1957). Colorimetric Method for the Determination of Serum Glutamic Oxaloacetic and Glutamic Pyruvic Transaminases. *Am J. Clin. Pathol.*, 28.Pp. 56-60.

Steel, R. G and Torrie, J. H (1980); Principles and Procedures of Statistics.A Biometrical Approach. 2nd Edition McGraw Hill Book Co. New –York.

Wright P. J. Leathward P. D and Plunner, D. T (1972a) Enzyme in rat urine:Alkaline Phosphatase. *Enzymologia.* 42.317 – 327.

Wright P. J. Leathward P. D and Plunner, D. T (1972b) Enzyme in rat urine: Alkaline Phosphatase. *Enzymologia.* 42.327 – 337.

Yakubu M. T and Akanji M. A (2003). Some Biochemical Changes in Selected rat tissues following Repeated Administration of Cimetidine. Book of Abstracts of 23rd Annual Conference of the Nigerian Society of Biochemistry and Molecular Biology, Ilorin, Nigeria. Pp.38-39.

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